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MODERN MOBILITY IN THE INTERORGANIZATIONAL INTEGRATION OF TOURISM

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Abstract: *The research aim was to show that mobility enables entertainment, leisure and activities, which are related to the relationships of people who travel and live in places outside their place of residence. By using statistical method we investigated the mobility of people, capital and resources, which creates organizational effects during organizational integration and gives concrete financial, capital, integration and other results of activities. The focus of the research was modern mobility, through which we sought mathematical or other measurement data. We used the obtained data to measure the state and development potentials. The theoretical part describes the descriptive method of literature review. Using the method of compilation we summarized the observations and conclusions of other authors, which we cited, the analysis of primary and secondary sources and we analysed data derived from our work and other described methods. We deduced conclusions through the deductive and inductive method and made calculations at the level of the used statistics through statistical data. Research has shown that mobility is an important segment of tourism and that tourism is a fast-growing but vulnerable activity, as minor economic, health, social or other crises have already shown that mobility and tourism are very sensitive areas that can stop quickly, due to harmful or unpredictable actions, which can, in turn, have serious economic consequences.*

Keywords: *organisation, interorganizational integration, mobility.*

MODERNA MOBILNOST V MEDORGANIZACIJSKI INTEGRACIJI TURIZMA

Povzetek: *Namen raziskave je bil pokazati, da mobilnost omogoča zabavo, prosti čas in dejavnosti, ki so povezane z odnosi med ljudmi, ki potujejo in živijo v krajih izven kraja bivanja. S statistično metodo smo raziskali mobilnost ljudi, kapitala in virov, ki ustvarja organizacijske učinke pri organizacijskem povezovanju in daje konkretne finančne, kapitalske, integracijske in druge rezultate delovanja. Raziskava se osredotoča na sodobno mobilnost, s pomočjo katere smo iskali matematične in druge merilne podatke. Pridobljene podatke smo uporabili za oceno obstoječega stanja in razvojnih potencialov. Teoretični del zajema pregled literature s pomočjo deskriptivne metode. Z metodo kompilacije smo povzeli opazanja in zaključke drugih citiranih avtorjev, analizo primarnih in sekundarnih virov ter analiziralo podatkov, ki izhajajo iz lastnih raziskav in drugih opisanih metod. Do sklepnih ugotovitev smo prišli z uporabo deduktivne in induktivne metode, izračune pa smo naredili na ravni uporabljene statistike preko statističnih podatkov. Raziskave so pokazale, da je mobilnost pomemben segment turizma in da je turizem hitro rastoča, a ranljiva dejavnost. Številne manjše gospodarske, zdravstvene, socialne in druge krize v preteklosti so namreč pokazale, da sta tako mobilnost kot tudi turizem zelo občutljivi panogi, ki ju škodljiva ali nepredvidljiva dejanja lahko hitro ustavijo in ohromijo, kar pa lahko ima resne gospodarske posledice.*

Ključne besede: *organizacija, interorganizacijska integracija, mobilnost.*

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Introduction

Due to the broad scope of the field, our research focused on tourism and tourist activities and defined mobility, with which we tried to explain interesting areas where it is increasingly necessary to study the organizational integration, supply and demand and especially interesting organization of mobility for the needs of tourism and tourist activities. If tourism can be defined as a term commonly understood as travel for entertainment, recreation and its accompanying activities, then tourism should be presented as a set of phenomena and relationships related to the activity of people traveling and staying in places outside their place of residence, continuously for up to one year, for either leisure, entertainment or business purposes. This is an area where main offers are activities such as rest, entertainment, food, travel, visits, and it needs to be noted that there are rare cases in which the same organization of either tourism or tourist activities has its own resources for the organization of transportation. This activity could be considered as outsourcing, but if we would compare it with industry or manufacturing company, the comparison would be unnecessary, because the organization of tourist transport (charter transport) is a special activity performed by qualified companies that are closely related to tourism, so we consider them as an organizational cooperation, which in general means a special mobility in space.

The term interorganizational integration is primarily meant as the interorganizational integration of organizations involved in industry, entrepreneurship, but it is quite realistic to use the concept in tourism, as tourism is an economic activity that is globally connected and possibly in addition to automotive, oil, technical activities forms one of the broadest international integration where transport and mobility are expressed as business equivalents. According to Zelenika, if we look at industry, logistics and transport, we come to the explanation that the organization of transport and related logistics processes enables transnational trade, industrial connection, expansion of market and market activities, globalization, movement of people and capital (Zelenika, 2010).

In this definition, it is possible to identify Slovenian transport organizations, which with their activity take care of tourist travel, passenger transport or delivery of semi-finished products for industrial production, finished products for international trade, and last but not least market expansion and market activities. Of course, mobile factors are important for the interorganizational integration in tourism and tourist activities, which are expressed in the use of technology, in innovation, in the recognition of modern forms of media space recognition. The author Gričar (2009) tells us that building interorganizational systems is a global challenge for developed economies, tourism and all other activities based on interconnection. The author Tomšič (2009) added the cultural values of the profiles of modern societies and their mobility, giving value shifts in the modern globalization society. The outline of future trends in economic development, in which we can directly take into account tourism and tourist activities, was given by the author Mencinger (2009), who explained how global crises can affect the development of individual countries and the development of individual GDP.

In the context of mobility, processes closely related to the tourist offer organization of tourist transport, conclusion of arrangements or tourist contracts are created during interorganizational integration, thus expressing important economic factors such as forwarding, preparation of documentation, preparation of goods for transport, wrapping, packing, loading, etc. Many authors that we will mention later on in the research have written about tourism and its organization, describing individual processes and organizing various trainings for their implementation. Much has been written about innovation (Beganović, 2016) and finding solutions for better organization of entrepreneurship in tourism. A lot has also been written about these processes in Slovene and foreign literature, which is undoubtedly of great help to tourism and other organizations, users and operators of transport activities (Murtič, Jankovič, 2019). Elements of business security are also important, which is expressed through legal transactions and the legal protection of individual transactions in tourism. Of particular interest is the legal protection of individuals who, in the interest of traveling, visiting and getting to know new tourist destinations, pay the agreed amounts without having the knowledge of how and in what way to ensure their safety and the security of their business. The authors Murtič and Jankovič (2020), in their monograph "Fundamentals of understanding legal relations in tourism", gave the basic legal knowledge for safe travel. Comparatively, tourists can read Jakomin, Jelenc and Vlačič (2006), who describe the foundations of freight forwarding in recent times, with Jakomin, Zelenika and Medeot (2002) describing the technology of transport and transport systems, Gajšek (2007) describing the basics of transport technology, Ogorelec (2004) describes international transport and logistics and Pavliha and Vlačič (2007) describe transport law and Pavliha and Simoniti (2007) insurance law. Everything is related with mobility, because it can be meaningfully used in the field of mobility of passengers, tourists and the like. Certainly, an important element of security is also knowing certain rights of passengers, tourists in the very phase of concluding deals and also the implementation of travel, as Murtič, Jankovič, Gerbec and Uhernik (2020) wrote. There are many other authors who describe individual procedures in mobility processes and during interorganizational integration, but due to the breadth of the task, it is impossible to mention them.

Purpose and objective of the research

The purpose and objective of the research was to determine how tourist organizations involved in the offer of tourist services manage their business organizationally and what are their business effects, given the crisis periods and fluctuations in tourist mobility. The basic purpose of the research was to give credible views on the actual situation in the tourism industry in a professional and argumentative way with the help of the theory of organizational and business sciences, taking into account internationally comparable relevant facts of development. In the research, we used the scientific and theoretical findings of individual authors related to the field. Unfortunately, we did not use specific statements or citations because the subject in question does not allow us to do so, and some data are a business secret and are not made available to the public. The findings enabled us to expand knowledge, identify the profession and enable the identification of new building blocks for the preparation of a unified model of interorganizational integration, and we received answers to the form and methods of tourist mobility in recent times.

Goals of our research were:

- define the concepts of theoretical starting points and determination of building blocks for interorganizational integration in the field of mobility,
- analyse the pre-existing situation and gain new insights for the dependent and intertwining field of success between interorganizational integration in view of economic changes in Slovenia, Europe and beyond,
- search for the model, which would allow us easier interorganizational integration of tourism organisations and their destinations,
- preparation of an appropriate mobility model that would be acceptable to tourism and service organizations as a model solution,
- confirmation or refutation of the statements set out in the hypotheses and at least indicate the possibilities for further development in the field of organizational management of modern mobility in tourism.

Key hypothesis

In our research, we did not study tourism as a tourist activity, but we looked for factors that we considered to have the greatest impact on the actual and future situation in the field of interorganizational integration and mobility in Slovenia. Based on them, we anticipated six key hypotheses and set them so that they follow each other in sequence, and at the same time we connected them in such a way that they are conditioned by the scope of the substance under consideration, namely:

- *Human resource management* is a key process in the interorganizational management of mobility, which proves that without man it is not possible to carry out procedures between organizational connections.
- *The choice of a specific model* among the interorganizational management of mobility is conditioned by the degree of maturity of each tourism organization.
- In the interorganizational management of mobility, there is an important *correlation between the quality of management* of an individual organization and its performance.
- *Mutual trust* in the management of various organizations is a condition for successful organizational management of mobility.
- *Effective mutual communication* is necessary for successful interorganizational management of mobility in tourism.
- *The modern paradigm* of interorganizational mobility management is based on the model of tourism management according to the global interests of tourists, which is reflected in the growing interest in visiting as many destinations in Slovenia, Europe and much broader.

Of course, the hypotheses were the basis for finding answers to the question of what are the global, mutual and interorganizational relations, through which the whole process between the organizational integration of tourism and transport organizations is regenerated.

It is a multi-year and multi-layered study and research of the field of mobility or interorganizational integration of tourism and transport organizations, which was the basis for setting appropriate hypotheses and preparing a research questionnaire. The prepared questionnaire was the basis for obtaining data with which we wanted to confirm or refute our claims. This is regarding modern paradigms that condition the change and systemic overlap of individual areas, which are economically conditioned and together synchronously form successful economic growth and GDP of an individual country.

Research methods

The research is based on the obtained data, which we processed virtually, obtained starting points and based on that, we created research questions. In developing the survey questionnaire, we proceeded from the assumptions and hypotheses defined in the introductory part of the research. We sensibly connected individual assumptions with hypotheses and then made statements for each hypothesis. We decided to determine the perception of the actual situation, as well as the desired (future) situation, for which we had to adjust the questionnaire accordingly. Such an approach allowed us to identify the gap between the perception of the actual and the desired state. A larger gap means a greater opportunity for improvement, which was our starting point for formulating proposals to improve the state of mobility. An improved situation would mean filling those exposed gaps, which in our case means tourist activity, which tells us that if there is more mobility, there is also more need for tourism services and vice versa, if there are more tourism orders there is also more mobility.

The prepared questionnaire required testing, which was carried out at 30 tourist organizations in Slovenia. After a successful test and identification of issues through which the process of managing mobility in tourism is regenerated, we addressed the questionnaire to several transport organizations throughout Slovenia. The presumption for the ideal sample was 150 returned and completed survey questionnaires, which should be sufficient for research and obtaining the necessary data. After the survey, we also received the estimated number of completed forms, but the inadequacy of some answers required the exclusion of a number of questionnaires from the analysis. The inadequacy of the samples was in the equality of answers, which, although applicable to a particular organization, are useless for finding mobility solutions. Due to the same answers, only one such sample can be used, which has led to others being excluded and identified as useless. The total number of responses received was a sufficient sample for analysis and survey research. For better identification, we performed quantitative, factorial and regressive research. The obtained data largely confirmed our hypotheses, which confirmed our assumption that in Slovenia there is no single model for interorganizational management of mobility in tourism. What this means depends on the use of data in tourism and tourist activity or in the field of mobility or transport of tourists to different destinations. There are some business ties between certain organizations, which can be considered as an interorganizational connection in terms of sociological or business science, but these are mostly smaller tourism and transport organizations, which are already connected by the type of supply and demand and the flow of business. When it comes to large and internationally connected organizations (example: a concern of hotels around the world), they have their own booking, their own organization, their own offers, overnight stays, travel, accommodation and specially organized mobility for their guests or tourists (Murtič, Jankovič, 2019).

It is interesting to note that these large organizations are more vulnerable in times of crisis than smaller organizations, as they cannot adapt to times of crisis, which also leads to a mobility crisis. Smaller organizations are more flexible, easier to adapt to technique, technology, changes and also modern mobility depending on the form of infrastructure and substructure (Zelenika, 2010).

Research results

To understand our research better, we would like to explain that in the questionnaire we relied on the actual or current situation, to which we addressed 33 questions, and the desired or future situation, to which we addressed 17 questions. With the first, we wanted to gain insight into the current situation in the field between the interorganizational integration of tourism organizations and mobility management. In the second set of questions, we focused on those areas that require change and which would allow us to find modern building blocks for the preparation of a unified model between organizational management of tourism, mobility, introduction of information systems, technology, digitalization and robots.

The obtained data were ideal for processing with the SPSS 19.0 package, which is already a bit outdated but useful and enables a comprehensive overview and a wider range of data processing. Data of the attributive (arithmetic) type were presented in the form of response frequencies, and contingency tables were used to show the relationships between variables. We calculated the basic statistical parameters, namely the arithmetic mean, minimum result, maximum result and standard deviation.

Table 1 and Table 2 show the average value of agreement with the given statements, which allowed the respondents to evaluate each stated statement with values on a five-point scale, with a score of 1 (lowest) meaning they don't agree with the statement and score 5 (highest) to fully agree with the statement. The value, which was higher in its value level, indicated the need for a certain regulation of the research field. We see this already in the first indent of the actual situation under B12, which says economic crises can negatively affect the tourism business, and shows the need for urgent changes and finding appropriate solutions. This assessment is followed by the next, which indicate the need for a unified model of interorganizational management of tourism and mobility, interorganizational cooperation, teamwork, innovation, cooperation with successful organizations, continuous cooperation, etc., as shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Assessments of the actual situation in the organization (Authors prepared a simulation with the obtained data with the SPSS 19.0 package)

Determination	Finding solutions to issues	Mean
B12	the health crisis has negatively affected our business	4.32
B33	a unified model of tourism and mobility management would help our organization	4.19
B5	in the case of mobility, our organization would always take into account the requirements of the client and adapt to them	4.07
B8	working with new and successful organizations has a positive impact on the success of our organization	3.94
B3	teamwork is successful and on a high level in our organization	3.88
B18	we have continuous cooperation with the same or recurring clients	3.88
B2	the level of foreign language skills of our employees is sufficient	3.81
B4	our organization is successful in making new contacts	3.81
B19	communication between different units and organizations is efficient and smooth, it could be better	3.81
B17	payment obligations are settled on time	3.80
B21	we regularly monitor changes in regulations	3.79
B31	permanent mobility is beneficial for our organization	3.79
B27	we operate in the circle of tourist associations	3.75
B1	the level of education of our management is appropriate and has a positive impact on the performance of our organization	3.74
B11	evaluation and rewarding in our organization are based on objective and fair criteria	3.71
B25	the work is organized in a way that it allows us to adapt quickly to change	3.71
B6	our organization is at a technologically high and demanding level	3.68
B9	we are efficient enough in identifying and solving problems	3.68
B16	we solve disagreements kindly and politely, there are no bad relationships	3.68
B13	conversations are open between management and subordinates	3.66
B15	management understands employee problems and strives to address them	3.64
B10	our organization has a positive climate and employee satisfaction	3.62
B32	we know the European model of tourism and mobility in tourism	3.57
B22	we have strong informal contacts with other organizations	3.53
B24	the running of our organization is democratic and networked	3.52
B26	we have an appropriate form of interconnection with other organizations	3.50
B28	our efficiency and effectiveness are greater within associations of organizations	3.50
B14	we have harmonized rules of operation	3.40
B20	knowledge of international and EU regulations is at an adequate level	3.39
B30	our form of organization is appropriate according to the requirements of the market for the needs of transport	3.37
B7	we have thoroughly crafted logistical support	3.26
B23	we know the customs and culture of other countries	2.91
B29	we know some successful tourism and mobility models	2.08

Relevant review of evaluated data in the field of desired or future situation also shows a high level of need for timely financial (movements) 4.69, the need for a unified methodology of tourism and mobility management related to tourism 4.47, the need for long-term cooperation and the need for modern mobility. Again, we set values that are also shown with statements ranging between 1 (lowest) and 5 (highest). Their analysis shows that confirmation scales have been set in the range of more than half, which indicates the necessary changes and the need for greater interorganizational integration, the introduction of new methods in tourism and especially in tourism mobility.

Table 2

Opinions on the ideal condition (Authors' own simulation of obtained data with SPSS 19.0 package)

Determination	Finding solutions to issues	Mean
C9	timely financial transactions (payments) are crucial to the success of the organization	4.69
C17	a common EU methodology in the field of tourism would affect our work	4.47
C8	long-term interorganizational collaboration has a positive impact on performance	4.22
C7	trust in employees enables the successful work of the organization	4.14
C10	appropriate cooperation with the creators of legal regulations would affect the efficiency and effectiveness of each organization	4.09
C6	open conversation with employees has a positive effect on the performance of the organization	4.06
C5	the satisfaction of our employees has a positive effect on the success of the organization	4.02
C16	subscribers of mobility services could adapt to tourism organizations and their needs	3.96
C2	greater efficiency in the organization is achieved by older and more experienced management	3.92
C4	friendly management of employees contributes to the success of the organization	3.84
C15	working within large associations helps to secure work	3.75
C1	younger and more educated management is more conducive to greater organizational efficiency	3.71
C3	hard leadership of employees contributes to the success of the organization	3.45
C14	just in time - can also be introduced in the field of tourism and mobility	3.32
C13	outsourcing is an appropriate form of implementing mobility in tourism	3.06
C12	the hotel model of tourism and mobility influences the interorganizational connection of tourist organizations and carriers in Slovenia	2.93
C11	can foreign tourism organizations influence as a model of successful interorganizational integration and mobility in tourism	2.31

We have two sets that demonstrate an imaginary situation that we can study, as the comparison of the ratings of both sets only shows us certain gaps between the actual situation and aspects that respondents consider important for the success and efficiency of their organization. The biggest gap is in the knowledge and implementation of business models, which affects both tourism and tourist activity as well as general mobility in this activity. From the content, we can conclude that the respondents expressed a strong need for changes and appropriate business models that would help them improve the performance and efficiency of their organization. At the same time, they show that their knowledge of already existing models is at a rather low level or they do not know them at all. This clearly tells us that it is not sensible or useful to transfer models from abroad directly to Slovenia, so one of the goals of our study in the future was to prepare an innovative model that would meet the specific needs of Slovenian tourism organizations and facilitate mobility and achieve goals.

We see that respondents globally agree that otherwise a uniform methodology in the field of tourism would affect their work (c17 - 4.47) and their organization. Above all, their clearly expressed need for a useful innovative model is important - the respondents believe that a unified model of tourism management and mobility in tourism would help their organization (b33 - 4.19). However, despite the expressed need for innovative business models, it is not clear if they have any prior weak knowledge of existing models, which means that they expect something new, and at the same time they are not ready to find models or solutions that exist abroad. The assessment of statement b29 "knowledge of foreign models" is only 2.08. Consistent with the low level of knowledge, is their assessment of the impact of both models on interorganizational integration (c11 - 2.31). Knowledge of the European model of providing tourist services and tourist mobility is slightly higher (b32 - 3.57), which stems from their practice and daily cooperation with various models in Europe and beyond. We know that many Slovenian tourist organizations provide various tourist and mobile services in Slovenia and at the same time cooperate with organizations in other European countries, regardless of the European Union.

We find that if the data of the actual situation (B12 - 4.32), as the highest value shows us that the health crisis can negatively affect our business and on the other hand (C9 - 4.69), as the highest value of the desired situation tells us that in order for timely payment of services in tourism and mobility to enable successful business, the following data (B33 - 4.19) of uniform model of tourist services and mobility would help organizations to be repeated in ideal condition (C17 - 4.47) an uniform tourist methodology of the EU would have a positive impact on the work of the organization, saying that the respondents want a unified model of the interorganizational management of tourism and mobility, while not being limited to Slovenia. How to understand and explain the results, if not in a way that shows respondents wanting a new innovative model of tourism management and mobility in tourism, but not a limitation to Slovenia, which again tells us that Slovenian tourism and with it tourism mobility in the European area is so related to foreign tourism, that in this sense the borders of state economies are disappearing and organizations and their interconnection are important.

As we have foreseen, a very important aspect is represented by the interpersonal human relations in tourism and mobility, and we see that there is still a lot of space and the need to improve the situation. Respondents agree that trust in employees (c7 - 4.14), open conversation with employees (c6 - 4.06), employee satisfaction (c5 - 4.02) and friendly management (c4 - 3.84) positively contribute to success of individual organizations and increase success in interorganizational networking.

In fact, we can conclude that the value assessments of the actual situation in tourism and mobility within tourism are low and that they indicate the need for improvement, especially in the areas between organizational integration and tourism management in times of crisis.

This need is particularly evident in the area of:

- harmonized rules of work (b14 - 3.40);
- democratic and network management of the organization (b24 - 3.52);
- positive climate and employee satisfaction (b10 - 3.62);
- understanding and elimination of employee problems by management (b15 - 3.64);
- open conversations between management and employees (b13 - 3.66);
- friendly and polite calming of tension (b16 - 3.68)
- evaluation and rewarding according to objective criteria (b11 - 3.71);

the gap between the opinion that timely financial transactions are decisive for the success of an individual organization (c9 - 4.69) and the actual timely settlement of payment obligations by the organizations from which the respondents come (b17 - 3.80) is also interesting and telling. Payment indiscipline is one of the problems most often mentioned by respondents as topical (60.7%). This may be due to the global health crisis, recession and poor economic situation, but it may be due to indiscipline and a poorly regulated area of law, but we do not have a proper argument for this claim.

The next area where the need for change and improvement is evident, is knowledge of regulations. Respondents believe that appropriate cooperation of tourism organizations with lawmakers would affect the efficiency and effectiveness of tourism and mobility (c10 - 4.09). At the same time, we note again that the actual knowledge of international and EU regulations is at a fairly low level (b20 - 3.39), as well as regular monitoring of official gazettes and publications of regulations is not sufficiently present (b21 - 3.79). We assume that the respondents are likely to leave the knowledge of the regulations to professional bodies and legal services or external contractors who take care of monitoring the publication of regulations, appropriate information and adaptation.

In the field of interorganizational cooperation, the picture is much more varied. Respondents largely agree that long-term organizational cooperation has a positive effect on performance (c8 - 4.22). However, they agree to a much lesser extent with the statement that the functioning of organizations within large associations is a condition for success and that it helps to provide work (c15 - 3.75). This tells us that the actual situation in their organizations shows a certain form between organizational networking and cooperation within associations, but not at a sufficient level. Evaluations of participation are as follows:

- have an appropriate form of interconnection with others (b26 - 3.50);
- their efficiency and effectiveness are higher within associations (b28 - 3.50);
- operating in the circle of tourist associations (b27 - 3.75);
- organized tourism and mobility are useful for their organization (b31 - 3.79);
- communication between different units and organizations is efficient and smooth (b19 - 3.81);
- have continuous cooperation with the same clients (b18 - 3.88);

thus, performance assessments in various areas of tourism and mobility show that the situation is solid, which is understood as a certain form of interorganizational integration, but it would still make sense to improve it at least slightly. We believe that the reasons for this are in the following answers, namely:

- the level of management education is appropriate and has a positive effect on the performance of the organization (b1 - 3.74);
- the organization is successful in making new contacts (b4 - 3.81);
- team work in the organization is successful and at a sufficiently high level (3.88);

in the field of tourism, organizations follow the guidelines and adapt to the requirements of tourists or clients of organized groups (b5 - 4.07), and the form of the organization itself is less appropriate for the needs of tourism (b30 - 3.37), because tourists or clients do not descend into it. A tourist, a group or association aims to obtain an appropriate and high-quality tourist service in the form of accommodation, excursions, sightseeing or mobility at the lowest possible cost.

Among the most pressing problems, the respondents most often mentioned financial indiscipline or excessively long payment deadlines (60.7%), unfair competition (29.2%), unregulated legislation (14.3), excessive costs (11.4%) and the presence of foreign tourist organizations on the Slovenian market (10%). Financial indiscipline could have been caused by the health crisis, unfair competition,

unregulated legislation, the presence of foreign tourist organizations in Slovenia, etc. however, we can confirm with certainty that the interorganizational management of tourism and mobility is disorganized.

The obtained data were also analysed by *factor data analysis*, which is a mathematical procedure (data are measurable and can be presented), where seemingly disordered data are grouped on the basis of individual factors and certain connections or deviations are identified. When analysing individual survey responses with the help of factor analysis, we found that certain questions coincide with a certain factor. How strong this connection is, can be told by the factor weight, which is actually a measure of the strength of the connection of individual survey responses with a single factor. The values range from -1 to +1, with a factor weight value ranging from 0.5 to + 0.5 meaning that there is no relationship between the question and the factor. Values between + 0.5 and + 0.7 mean sufficient, values between + 0.7 and + 0.8 mean good, and values above + 0.8 mean very good linear correlation (according to the principle, the more A, the more B). Negative values of the factor weight tell us the negative linear correlation (according to the principle, the more A, the less B). The interpretation of an individual factor is subject to an assessment of which issues coincide with an individual factor.

The factor analysis of the questionnaire used, shows that 69.3% of the variance of answers in lot **b** (assessment of the actual situation in the organization of respondents) explains 7 components. These, however, are not equivalent to each other, as the first component is explained by 18.83% of the variance, the second by 14.48%, the third by 8.14%, and so on.

With the questions in section **b**, we therefore measured 7 aspects of the situation in tourist organizations:

- the factor "relations in the company" is linked to 9 statements with weights from 0.779 to 0.510;
- 5 statements with a weight of 0.737 to 0.552 are related to the factor "work organization and interorganizational cooperation");
- 4 statements with weights from 0.695 to 0.495 are linked to the factor "knowledge of models and partners";
- 3 statements with weights from 0.667 to 0.460 are linked to the factor "performance" (leadership, team work, networking);
- 3 statements with weights from 0.853 to 0.615 are linked to the "mobility" factor;
- 3 statements with weights from 0.756 to 0.512 are linked to the "regulations" factor);
- 2 statements with weights of 0,728 and -0,537 are linked to the last factor.

In the **c** set of questions (ideal or desirable situation according to the respondents), 3 components explain 61% of the variance of answers. The components are fairly balanced with each other, as the first component is explained by 25.8% variance, the second by 17.8% and the third by 17.55%.

With the questions under point 3, we therefore measured 3 aspects of the desired situation according to the respondents. These three aspects are also partly covered in the **b** set of questions;

- statements with weights from 0.886 to 0.718 are related to the factor "relations in the organization";
- 3 statements with weights from 0.822 to 0.570 are related to the factor "knowledge of tourist models";
- 4 statements with weights from 0.809 to 0.471 are linked to the factor "interorganizational cooperation".

We realized that deviations or confirmations of individual factors or individual groups of factors that explain the reasons for deviations or confirmations of individual statements between the actual and desired situation in the interorganizational management of tourism services and mobility and we used it to find key causes that change the situation.

We prepared a regression analysis of independent and dependent variables in which we looked for factor causes. In the relationship between the identified variances of the actual and desired state, it made sense to find variances that indicate the causes of deviation or uniformity of individual variances considering the causal factor. Based on these, *the regression analysis* showed independent and dependent variables with respect to variances of the inflation factor, which was within acceptable limits of 1,40; 1,88; 1,95, which is shown in the test below.

Independent variables are included in f1-f7 - latent factors from factor analysis and dependent variables are included in F1-revenue, $R^2 = 0,32$, $p = 0,00000$ ***, f5, f6, f7 are statistically significantly related to f1 -income, partial coefficients, which is reflected in -0,468, $p = 0,000000$, 0,343 $p = 0,00018$ and 0,260 $p = 0,00050$.

The variance of the inflation factor is within variable limits: 1,40; 1, 88; 1,95.

Prediction equation for: "f1_income"

$$\text{"f1_income"} = -39039126, -87010536, *f5 + 66251209,8 * f6 + 39473037,2 * f7$$

For the general reader, the data are very demanding or even uninteresting, but for those familiar with the study methodology or research associates, the data are useful and provide a starting point for preparing new research or discovering new success factors in

tourism and mobility within tourism. Of course, researchers are aware that our research is just an attempt to declaratively present a collection of data obtained from the survey and use this data for new models or at least by confirming the suitability of certain factors in tourism and mobility for tourism, which is a research success.

Discussion and confirmation of hypotheses

Talking about the success or failure of an individual research is completely irrelevant, as all research is subject to reading, verification and evaluation, but its purpose is primarily to arouse a wider circle of researchers to try something new in a theoretical or practical way. As a result, we come to the conclusion that the findings of quantitative, factor and regression analysis tell us that there is an organizational link between tourism and mobile organizations, but it is closely linked to tourism service or mobility and does not give results in other areas that could more important in supporting of tourism and mobility. Otherwise, most of the variants confirm our assumption that it is hard to talk about a unified model of interorganizational management of tourism or mobility in tourism in Slovenia, because it does not exist. There are guidelines for the development of tourism and mobility, which are reflected throughout the development of tourism (MGRT, 2020) and the strategy for the development of tourism in municipalities, the strategy of sustainable growth of Slovenian tourism and many other strategies and instructions on how to organize for the growth of tourism, but it is hard to talk about a specific model or even less about a single model of tourism, tourist activity and mobility within tourism. The Act on the Promotion of Tourism Development (Law on the promotion of tourism development, Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia, No. 13/18) is also interesting, but its provisions are directly related to tourism and tourist activity, which we could use in certain parameters, but this law was not the basis for our research. There is also no legal basis that would require interorganizational integration, as individual organizations are legal entities that enter into legal transactions independently and with the consent of the will, which again is not related to our research, although we used certain results (Murtič, Jankovič, 2018). This also confirms our claim that most of the interorganizational connections run through the system of acquaintanceship, which allow the conclusion of transport transactions, while only a small part of transport organizations is involved in international organizations that take over and organize transport (Jankovič, Murtič, 2019).

We realized that a unified model of the interorganizational management of tourism and tourist activities and mobility within tourism would simplify the procedures and organization within tourism. Individual tourism organizations would carry out the work for which they are registered, and mobility would be left to transport organizations that have adequate means of transport and for which mobility is their main activity. All organizations should have equal access to individual offers and mobility. Certified business excellence of an individual organization or group of organizations, even though they have a quality certificate, does not reflect a unified business in the field of tourism and tourist activities, much less business excellence in mobility. It can only be a form of good practice that can otherwise be used and positively passed on to other organizations.

We realized that managing tourism and tourist activities, managing mobility and organizational, economic, interpersonal, intercultural, linguistic, professional, educational and other differences is a demanding task, without which it is impossible to organize activities, provide material goods and carry out other activities that are necessary and important for society.

To confirm the established data, we performed a regression multiple analysis with the aim of determining the situation that could be renewed, changed and improved. Unfortunately, the analysis of the answers clearly showed a situation that is not favourable for Slovenian tourism and mobility in tourism and confirms the existing situation that we assumed. Respondents showed the need for improvement and were willing to adopt a unified model of the interorganizational management of tourism and mobility, insofar as this would improve their activity and business. The review of the obtained answers to individual questions gave answers to individual assumptions in the set hypotheses:

1. In the first, we set the variance that human resource management is a key process in the interorganizational management of logistics processes. This was followed in the survey of the existing and desired situation by questions related to the level of education, the level of knowledge and use of foreign languages, teamwork and mutual relations, and relations with superiors. The finding showed us that the average score is 3.88, which confirms the hypothesis and demonstrates the importance of human resource management in the organizational management of tourism, tourist activities and mobility;
2. in the second, we set up a specific model as a variance that gives the values and conditions for entering this model under the same or different conditions. With questions about the performance of the organization, harmonized rules of work, knowledge of regulations, knowledge of other models, etc. we obtained answers that confirm the hypothesis. The average score is 3.50, which tells us that a specific model is urgently needed, it should improve the business and performance of tourism organizations. An appropriate rating would be a rating above 4.5 - 5.0, which tells us that there is still a lot of room for improvement;
3. in the third, we assumed that there is an important correlation between the quality of management of an individual organization and successful interorganizational management of tourism and tourist activities and mobility. Under the questions

evaluation and rewarding, continuous cooperation between the same organizations, the form of interconnection, work organization, etc. we received an average score of 3.71, which again shows us that there is still enough room in this area to introduce new correlations for successful leadership;

4. in the fourth case, we assumed that the mutual trust of the managements of the participating organizations in the interorganizational integration is a condition for successful operations, which proved to be appropriate. Leaders of organizations give their added value and thus contribute to a more successful interorganizational cooperation and management of tourism and tourist activity, and especially mobility within tourism;
5. in the fifth, we assumed that mutual communication is a key condition for successful interorganizational management of tourism. When asked about identifying and resolving problems, economic, health or other crises, payment indiscipline, knowledge of international regulations, organization, appropriateness of the form of interconnection, etc. we received an average score of 3.50, which again confirms the importance of mutual communication for the successful of it;
6. in the sixth part, in the research work, through the hypothesis of a modern paradigm of the interorganizational management of tourism, tourist activity and mobility, we asked the question of the existence of a unified methodology of tourism management, looking for the core of the research purpose. Thus, we assume that in Slovenia there is no uniform methodology for managing tourism, tourist activities and mobility within tourism.

We are aware that the discussion was constructive, covering the necessary levers and data that demonstrated mathematically measurable data, but it should be noted that this is only an individual experiment that is far from realistic or being the only one. Therefore, the way is open to search for new possibilities, new experiments, new models and new research. Our case served more as an example of good practice, although it was a scientific study that required a number of activities, analysis, verification, and expert judgment.

Conclusion

In the concluding part, we can say that through research and verification of the acquired variances, we confirmed our assumption about the existence or non-existence of a uniform methodology for tourism management, tourist activity and mobility within tourism. The common opinion was that the research field could be approached with the development of a unified methodology of interorganizational integration and management of tourism, tourist activity and mobility in tourism. We are aware that the survey could not cover the entire population and all tourism organizations, but given the condition that we surveyed a good part of tourism organizations from all over Slovenia, we believe that we covered such a sample that reflects the same issues of others, which it also confirmed the bankruptcy of large tourism organizations affected by economic, health and other crises. We recognized the need for innovative changes and the introduction of novelty systems, the introduction of technology, technical good, information systems, autonomous devices and robotics.

Our opinion is that the role of the state and its bodies would be important in the preparation of a unified model, which could facilitate the transition flows of tourism and tourist activities through legal regulations, while mobility would be improved with the existing form of mobility. A single model of interorganizational management of tourism should include standards of aggregation, requirements for a uniform form of organization and uniform form of implementation of tourist services or products, uniform criteria for the type and form of mobile means, uniform access to all transport, uniform interorganizational integration, coordination and complementarity, a uniform search for solutions, at least approximately comparable prices and tourism requirements. We estimated that the model of interorganizational management of tourism could be called "Modern mobility in the interorganizational integration of tourism."

As the data obtained in the research confirmed the hypotheses and showed the need for a unified model of tourism management, tourist activities and mobility for tourism, we have prepared a model together with tourist organizations for this purpose as an appendix to the monograph "Fundamentals of understanding legal relations in tourism", and will correct and offer it to all tourist organizations in Slovenia for use.

We are aware that we have taken only one small step towards easier and more successful interorganizational management of tourism, tourist activity and mobility within tourism, as tourism is an activity that is constantly evolving, adapting and changing, so there is still much room for new generations, for new research and finding better solutions.

References:

1. Ambrož, M., (2002), *Alternativa razvoja humane paradigme post-industrijske organizacije [An alternative to the development of the human paradigm of post-industrial organization]*, doktorska disertacija, Univerza Maribor, Fakulteta za organizacijske vede Kranj 2002.
2. Beganović, I., A., (2016), *Inovativnost strategijska orijentacija malih poduzeća [Innovation and strategic orientation of small businesses]*, Novi sad, Ueropromet, 2016, Mala knjiga plus, ISBN 978-86-017387-6-1, Novi Sad 2016, str. 185-302.
3. Čizman, A., Urh, M., (2008), *Izboljšanje konkurenčnosti podjetij z optimizacijo logističnih procesov [Improving the competitiveness of companies by optimizing logistics processes]*, 5. mednarodna logistična konferenca, Celje 2008.
4. Gajšek, B., (2007), *Osnove transportne tehnologije [Fundamentals of transport technology]*, Fakulteta za logistiko, Celje, e-gradivo 2007.
5. Gričar, J., (2009), *Izrabljanje informacijske tehnologije za inovativno med organizacijsko povezovanje [Utilizing information technology for innovative inter-organizational networking]*. Fakulteta za organizacijske študije Novo mesto, 21. Forum odličnosti in mojstrstva, Otočec 2009, ISBN 978 961 – 92652-0-8, str. 123-136.
6. Jakomin, I., Jelenc, M. in Vlačič, P. (2006). *Temelji poslovanja špedicije [The fundamentals of business forwarding]*. Portorož: Fakulteta za pomorstvo in promet.
7. Jakomin, L., Zelenika, R., Medeot, M., (2002), *Tehnologija prometa in transportni sistemi [Transport technology and transport systems]*, Fakulteta za pomorstvo, Portorož 2002.
8. Jankovič, P., Murtič, S., (2019), *Osnove pogodbenega prava v logistiki [Fundamentals of contract law in logistics]*, učbenik za visoke in univerzitetne programe, Arema, Visoka šola za regionalni management Rogaška Slatina.
9. M. Pavliha in S. Simoniti (2007). *Zavarovalno pravo. [Insurance law]* Gospodarski vestnik, Ljubljana.
10. Mencinger, J., (2009), *Oris prihodnjih trendov ali kaj po krizi? [Outline of future trends or something after the crisis?]* Fakulteta za organizacijske študije Novo mesto, 21. forum odličnosti in mojstrstva, Otočec 2009, ISBN 978 961 – 92652-0-8, str. 107-122.
11. MGRT – Ministrstvo za gospodarski razvoj in tehnologijo [Ministry of Economic Development and Technology] (2018). *Celostni razvoj turizma [integrated tourism development]*. Retrieved May 2018 from <https://www.gov.si teme/celostni-razvoj-turizma/>
12. Murtič, S., (2012), *Sodobna paradigma medorganizacijskega obvladovanja logističnih procesov [Modern paradigm of interorganizational management of logistics processes]*, Doktorska disertacija, Fakulteta za uporabne družbene študije v Novi Gorici, FUDŠ Nova Gorica, strani 100-123.
13. Murtič, S., Jankovič, P., (2018), *Osnove gospodarskega prava v logistiki [Fundamentals of commercial law in logistics]*, Arema Visoka šola za regionalni management Rogaška Slatina.
14. Murtič, S., Jankovič, P., (2019), *Model med organizacijskega povezovanja v fokusu gospodarskega razvoja [The model of organizational integration in the focus of economic development]*, Arema Visoka šola za regionalni management, Rogaška Slatina, znanstvena monografija, str. 36-241.
15. Murtič, S., Jankovič, P., Gerbec, Potočnik, R., Franko, Uhernik, I., (2020), *Osnove razumevanja pravnih razmerij v turizmu [Fundamentals of understanding legal relations in tourism]*, Arema, Visoka šola za regionalni management Rogaška Slatina, strokovna monografija, str. 175-283.
16. Ogorelec, A., (2004), *Mednarodni transport in logistika [International transport and logistics]*, Ekonomsko poslovna fakulteta Maribor, Maribor 2004.
17. Pavliha, M., Vlačič, P. (2007). *Prevozno pravo 2.del [Transport law, part 2]*. Spremenjena in dopolnjena izdaja. Gospodarski vestnik, Ljubljana.
18. Tomšič, M., (2009), *Vrednostni premiki v sodobni globalizirani družbi in odličnost. [Value shifts in a modern globalized society and excellence]*. Fakulteta za organizacijske študije Novo mesto, 21. forum odličnosti in mojstrstva, Otočec 2009, ISBN 978 961 – 92652-0-8, str. 47-73.
19. *Zakon o spodbujanju razvoja turizma. [The Act on the Promotion of Tourism Development]*. Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia, No. 13/18.
20. Zelenika, R., (2005), *Logistički sustavi [Logistics systems]*, Ekonomski fakultet u Rijeci, Republika Hrvatska, Turističnologistični sustavi, str. 508-512.
21. Zelenika, R., (2010), *Ekonomika prometne industrije [Economics of the transport industry]*, Ekonomski fakultet u Rijeci, Republika Hrvatska, ISBN 978-953-6148-69-1, znanstvena knjiga, str. 375-394.